

PROBLEMS OF GIVING LEXICON WITHOUT ALTERNATIVE IN SIMULTANEOUS TRANSLATION

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Abstract: Simultaneous translation is one of the most complex types of interpreting, and this type of translation is performed using special equipment. It is a method of oral translation in which the speaker conveys the content of the speech to the audience without the help of an interpreter.

Keywords: Simultaneous Translation, Communicative Media, Pragmalinguistic Competence, Sociopragmatic Competence.

Translation is as old as human relations, it is a means of expression between different peoples, bringing closer and bridging the gap between them, and then it is a means to connect communication and civilization, yes It is a strong rope that binds humanity all over the world. and is a bridge.

Until the end of the twenties, consecutive translation was used at international congresses, conferences and meetings, and after listening to the speaker's speech, it was translated into other working languages. Depending on the number of special languages adopted in the meeting of multilingual delegates, each speech was repeated from the podium several times in a row, which caused a great loss of time. From the end of the twenties, the translation of speeches began to be performed episodically at the same time as listening to them, and therefore received the name simultaneous translation.

Perhaps what interests us in this regard and we want to dwell on its methods in more detail is the translation of the conferences, because it is a suitable and clear view between the two guests, between whom there is synchronicity or og communicate through translation. In-depth knowledge of languages is an absolute prerequisite for the translator's practice, regardless of the translator's training and qualifications, if he wants to achieve the highest goal by translating his official speeches in international forums, he must be familiar with them. A simultaneous interpreter relays speech, unlike an interpreter struggling with a written text. Therefore, he hears it, imitates it in his mind, stores it in his memory and reformulates it in another language, works with a difficult and unique ability to create a new meaning in another language, and conveys the meaning to the listener by cleverly approaching it.

Based on the above, in this article, we want to explain the origin and development of simultaneous interpretation and the differences of simultaneous interpretation from other interpretations, the instructions necessary for the simultaneous interpretation in international congresses, conferences and meetings, and the shortcomings of simultaneous interpretation. and we set out to interpret following the most important rules that accompany translation from the speaker's speech to the listener.

The Origins and Development of Simultaneous Interpretation: Translation was and still is seen as a bridge between cultures and other societies without permission. It plays a major role in creating conditions for establishing dialogue between different cultures, reducing and eliminating the gap between different civilizations and cultures, and creating a common global thought. The question of translation also brings us to the level of the relationship between the author and the translator, to speak of translation as a creative process. When we examine the elements and methods of translation, we see that there is not much difference between authorship and translation. Both are creative works, because the translator usually does not create the translated text all at once, but rather has to use words and pronunciation as terms, choosing style and meaning in a specific way, and using it intelligently. It should be noted here that the first attempts at interpretation were made by André Kaminker in 1934.

It happened when he translated Hitler's speech on French radio [1, 17]. After that, after the Second World War, in 1945-1946, the Nuremberg International Military Court organized in Germany, simultaneous interpretation was used for the first time in the process of judging Nazi crimes [2, 134]. At first, the proposal of simultaneous translation confused many people involved in translation work and translation studies.

The problems of simultaneous translation in Russian translation studies began to be considered seriously after the 70s and 80s of the 20th century. An example of this is the work of researchers such as A.D. Schweizer, G.V. Chernov, and V.M. Ilyukhin. At this point, it is worth noting that the issues of simultaneous translation have not been well worked out in Uzbek translation studies. Only translator G'. Salomov's textbook "Introduction to the Theory of Translation".

It is known to us that it was emphasized that "interpreters-experts who are engaged in simultaneous translation and film shooting should clearly distinguish between the "language" of gestures" [5]. Nowadays, the study of foreign languages is widespread, and although most professionals have reached the level of knowledge of two or more languages, the need for simultaneous translation is still increasing.

Many types of translation are used nowadays, including simultaneous translation, and today we see that the importance of simultaneous translation in many institutions has become commonplace among many people. Like other translations, simultaneous translation has its own types, and this translation also has legal rules and conditions and methods of execution. In fact, the meaning of simultaneous translation includes several meanings according to the tasks and tools. We will discuss and explain all these rules and methods as much as possible. Importance of simultaneous interpretation: Translation means the translation of spoken or written texts from the original language into the second language while maintaining the same meaning. Also, if we take the word synchronous, it means to happen in an instant, Similarly, if you take the word synchronous, it means an instantaneous event, that is, the word synchronous takes the characteristic of immediate and instantaneous speed. . We can say that simultaneous translation is the translation of speech or texts from the original language into another language while preserving the full meaning of the original language. Here are some notes on this definition:

1. Synchronous translation is included in translation types according to the execution time of this type of translation. In addition to this type, there are also types of short translation and extended translation.

2. In this type of translation, it can be said that speed is the main determinant of the process, but the speed of work does not mean to ignore the need to translate the text between the two languages he is translating in the same sense and deliver it to the listener.

3. It should be mentioned among these tariffs. This concept of simultaneous translation can lead us to some applications that translate texts in real time [6, 87].

The most important areas where simultaneous interpretation is used: There are many meetings and international conferences where the use of simultaneous interpretation is necessary and indispensable, and this interpretation is a conversation between diplomats and delegations, these interviews are directly Whether it is face-to-face or indirect, whether the interview takes place in one place, or whether it is broadcast or over the Internet, the following are the most important of these situations:

1. Conferences: There are many international conferences attended by many nationalities and in these conferences interpreters speak several languages and here the conference management allocates interpreters to convey the speech in the conference, for example we often see conferences. the participants wear headphones because these headphones are the means by which the translation is transmitted to them. It includes seminars, meetings, international forums and many other meetings and conferences.

2. Media materials: When broadcasting the facts of an event live, for example (a session of the United Nations), some media outlets will need to allocate a simultaneous interpreter for simultaneous interpretation of all the speeches in that session.

3. Meetings or interviews: When a foreign delegation arrives in an Arab country, we see that some of this delegation is accompanied by an interpreter, so whether they are at the airport, in a restaurant or in other places, the interviews are considered a process of simultaneous interpretation. where the interpreter acts as an intermediary between the guests and the other party [7].

Conditions that must be fulfilled in this type of translation: Interpretation is governed by many conditions that govern its mechanism of action. These conditions mainly ensure correct translation results during the translation process. Also, these conditions take into account each type of simultaneous translation. This is because each type has its own characteristics in terms of application and performance. Below we summarize the most important of these terms:

1. The translator must be time-sensitive, that is, the translator must start the translation as soon as the speaker finishes speaking and phrases, so that the translated sentence can be spoken or written.

2. When translating into simultaneous translation media, the montage should match the sound or text, and synchronization should be taken into account, which is the simultaneous pronunciation of the phrase by the speaker as the output of the translation.

3. The simultaneous interpreter should strive to convey the meaning as it is, and the inaccuracy of the transmitted meanings as a result of laxity or lack of attention here is the reason for many mistakes in simultaneous translation. leads to [8].

Types of simultaneous interpretation: There are many types and classifications of simultaneous interpretation that correspond to the essence of simultaneous interpretation, and most of these classifications are the type of translation used in interpreting. Also, some classifications of translation according to the method of presentation of the translation are generally considered as the main types of translation.

First: Simultaneous media translation: This is the most common type of translation, as we often see the translation appear in the media with the direct speech of the speaker, and many others sections are of this type, namely:

1. Transliteration: This is what we see on the bottom line of the TV screen. Where the speaker is speaking and the written translation are shown at the bottom of the screen.

2. Spoken translation: Here, media representatives lower the speaker's voice and highlight the voice of an interpreter who quickly translates each word he hears and broadcasts to the listener.

3. Radio and television interpretation: Simultaneous interpretation is not included in written media. Rather, it is limited to radio and television, and if the translation is for radio content, it is called radio, and television, if it is for television content.

The second: Electronic translation: there is no real translator to do the translation, but rather an electronic program that downloads this type of translation immediately, and this application is designed for written texts or spoken words [9, 65].

Multiple translation methods of simultaneous interpretation In this type of translation, the translation is complete and perfect, and the translator uses many methods to perform his task, and these methods differ depending on the nature of the tools used in the translation process or the form of the tools provided in this translation. will be Each of these methods indicates a factor that determines the steps a translator must follow in performing this type of translation. We present these methods with as much explanation and commentary as we can:

First: Listening and delivery method: In this method, two parties work in translation, that is, a speaker and an interpreter, where the speaker delivers the text in the original language to the interpreter, and the interpreter immediately translates what he heard. However, the method may also involve a third party transmitter, which may be a computer that quickly writes and sends the translated text to the translator, or a person who delivers the translation in written form to the desired location. Second: Interpreting method: Here the interpreter listens to the speech and immediately translates and pronounces the text in dialogue form for others to hear.

Third: Quantitative translation method: in which the translator translates a certain number of phrases, paragraphs or words and then pronounces them, for example, the translator listens or watches five sentences, then immediately translates them, then translates another five sentences... and etc.

Fourth: Congruent interpretation: In this method of interpretation, there is an agreement between the speaker and the interpreter, for example, the speaker speaks on a certain topic for no more than two minutes, then he remains silent and the interpreter initiates the translation and delivers it to the audience [10, 19].

How is this type of translation done? The mechanism of implementation of this type of translation is still not approved by specific legal regulations. Because this type of translation depends on the vocabulary of both languages and the ability of the translator (to translate from the original language to the target language). The most important skills and abilities required for a translator to perform this translation are:

1) linguistic competence. It includes pragmatic competence. Pragmatic competence is divided into 2:

a) pragmalinguistic competence means, according to R. Setton, knowing the "specific shades of meaning" of certain words or phrases;

b) sociopragmatic competence is an etiquette, functional style and includes such broad concepts as knowing etc.

2) a synchronist should be able to build a general and special vocabulary, have sufficient general knowledge. This is necessary in order to gain an understanding of specific topics and to translate the given documents and lectures.

3) having the simultaneous interpreter's message processing skills or strategies or abilities [11, 58].

The translator must be familiar with the basic scientific terms that will be spoken and expected to be spoken at international conferences. In the process of simultaneous translation, even small elements cannot be left out of consideration. Since the microphone in the translation booth is very sensitive, the sound of the booth activities should be very quiet. Even the slow sound of turning the pages of the book and the large earrings worn by the female translator become a great noise in the listeners' ears [12].

Summary. So, simultaneous translation is the most complicated type of interpretation, and in this type of translation, translation is carried out using special equipment. This is a method of oral translation, which provides the content of the speech to the listeners without the presence of an interpreter during the speaker's speech. In the field of simultaneous translation and related to this topic, many translation scientists, researchers and masters have given their opinions and comments related to acquisition in several scientific-theoretical articles and monographs. we must learn.

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